

Weed species recorded in rice seedling nurseries in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate of Egypt, 1992 summer season.

Weed species	Family	Absolute presence ^a (n = 30)	Constancy ^b
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	28	0.93
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Poaceae	27	0.90
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	24	0.80
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	21	0.70
<i>E. oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	17	0.57
<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (Vahl) Panzer	Poaceae	16	0.53
<i>Bergia capensis</i> L.	Elatinaceae	10	0.33
<i>Cyperus longus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	10	0.33
<i>E. phyllopogon</i> (Stapf.) Koss.	Poaceae	9	0.30
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	9	0.30
<i>A. multiflora</i> Roxb.	Lythraceae	9	0.30
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	8	0.27
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	Poaceae	8	0.27
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	7	0.23
<i>A. auriculata</i> Willd.	Lythraceae	7	0.23
<i>Lemna gibba</i> L.	Lemnaceae	6	0.20
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	5	0.17
<i>Lotus arabicus</i> L.	Fabaceae	4	0.13
<i>Chara</i> sp.	Characeae	3	0.10
<i>Azolla pinnata</i> R. Br.	Azollaceae	2	0.07

^aNumber of nurseries in which the species was recorded. ^bNumber of nurseries in which the species was recorded/total number of nurseries surveyed.

weed control. Hand weeding cannot control *Echinochloa* spp. due to their morphological similarities with rice seedlings; they are therefore transplanted with rice.

The farmers all pulled seedlings in bunches, along with the soil, to avoid making rice seedling bundles. This is another practice that results in transplanting rice and weeds, including *E. crus-galli*, *E. oryzoides*, *E. colona*, and *C. difformis*.

Between 5 and 30% of rice hills were infested with transplanted weeds, which are highly competitive with rice. ■

Farming systems

Slash-and-burn upland rice production in Bolivia's chapare region

J. A. Litsinger, 1365 Jacobs Place, Dixon, CA 95620, USA; E. Ayala and D. Cruz, Instituto Boliviano de Tecnología Agropecuaria, Casilla no. 4067, Cochabamba, Bolivia

The chapare region of the Department of Cochabamba in Bolivia is located at the foot of the Andes in the Amazonian lowlands. Soils are acidic with pH of 4.0-5.5. Annual rainfall declines progressively from 5,000 mm in the southwest to 2,500 mm in the northeast. Bolivia has more than 120,000 ha of rice; all of it is upland on nonsloping land, and most is grown under mechanization on large farms. More than 15,000 ha are planted under slash-and-burn culture, however, which represents 6-10% of the country's total rice production of 225,000 t. About two-thirds of Bolivia's slash-and-burn

rice is planted in the chapare. Farmers have holdings of 5-50 ha. Lowland farm families consume an average 0.6-1.2 t milled rice per year. We interviewed 31 farmers from eight villages in Mar 1993 to describe the prevailing system of rice culture.

Rice is normally planted in Oct with the onset of the wet season. The forest is cleared from Jul to Sep during dry season. Farmers slash brush and fell trees (*chacear*), with time spent clearing depending on number of trees and average tree diameter. Virgin forests require a mean 36 d/ha to clear while regrowth (*chume*) requires a mean 26 d/ha. Brush and trees are left to dry for 1-2 mo before burning. Logs left after the first burn are piled for a second burning (9 d/ha).

On cleared virgin forest land, farmers usually plant two rice crops, followed by maize and/or cassava in the third year. The land is fallowed for an average of 7 yr before being returned to rice.

On the chume land, few soils are

sufficiently fertile for two consecutive rice crops. Land is left fallow for an average of 3 yr after cropping. In richer chume soils, banana follows the second year; in poorer soils, citrus and other fruits are planted. In the least fertile chume areas, rice is planted after clearing, and land is then fallowed for 3-7 yr before again planting rice.

Most popular cultivars are long-grained and about 1 m tall. Blue Bonnet was grown by 31% of the farmers during the 1992-93 season, followed by Pico Negro (23%), Carolina (22%), Blue Belle (8%), Cateto (8%), CICA8 (4%), Dominicana (2%), and Argentina (2%). Blue Bonnet, CICA8, Dominicana, and Argentina mature in 140 d, the others in 90 d. Farmers prefer later maturing cultivars for higher yield and earlier maturing ones to escape pests or for more immediate food consumption.

Seeds are planted in hills 25-40 cm apart using a dibble stick; on average, 9 seeds/hill are used. No purchased fertilizer is used. Virgin forest land

require an average of 0.8 weeding (mean of 8 d/ha) the first year and 1.6 weedings (17 d/ha) the next compared with chume land at 2.3 weedings (21 d/ha). Fifty-four percent of farmers sprayed insecticide for the large plant-sucking insect *petilla* (*Tibraca limbativentris*) or seed bugs. Some farmers reported losses to *petilla* of 50-80%.

Rice is harvested panicle-by-panicle with a hand knife, and threshing is done by foot. Rice is not winnowed. Yields

reported from the past two seasons averaged 0.8 t/ha. The highest yield any farmer obtained was 3.7 t/ha.

All of the farmers indicated weeds and lack of fertility to be their most important constraints, followed by *petilla* (80% of respondents). Other problems were mentioned by less than 27% of the farmers.

Other insect pests are grasshoppers and spittle bug (*Zulia* sp.). Common diseases are both leaf and neck blast,

brown leaf spot, narrow brown spot, and leaf scald. Blast is the most important of these, but it does not cause yield loss every year.

Because of the high labor input involved in slash-and-burn rice culture and stagnated yields, rainfed puddled rice culture might be an alternative in this high-rainfall area. ■

Yield ability and net return of rice-based cropping sequences under different water regimes in Bihar, India

U. K. Prasad, T. N. Prasad, and R. D. Singh, Agronomy Department, Rajendra Agricultural University (RAU), Bihar, Pusa (Samastipur) 848125, India

Due to availability of irrigation water in India's northern Bihar region, rice-based sequences of two or three crops a year have replaced the traditional rice monocrop. Irrigation water availability varies in the region.

We studied the performance of various cropping sequences under different water regimes. The experiment was conducted in a medium lowland site at the RAU Farm with five cropping sequences: rice - wheat - green gram, rice - winter maize - black gram, rice - potato - green gram, rice - Indian mustard - green gram, and rice - gram (chickpea) - green gram. Three levels of irrigation treatments were used in winter and summer seasons based on either irrigation water depth-cumulative pan evaporation ratio (IW:CPE) or days after sowing. Early rice variety Saket was transplanted on 20-25 Jul during 1986-91;

Table 2. Rice equivalence yield and net profit as influenced by irrigation levels and types of cropping sequences.^a Bihar, India. 1986-91.

Crop sequence	Level of irrigation					
	Suboptimal		Optimal		Supraoptimal	
	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Rice - wheat - green gram	7.9	343.4	8.2	360.7	8.7	377.6
Rice - winter maize - black gram	8.7	360.2	9.4	395.2	9.9	409.8
Rice - potato - green gram	12.6	409.9	14.5	519.2	15.2	544.1
Rice - Indian mustard - green gram	6.9	283.5	7.7	322.3	8.2	343.0
Rice - gram - green gram	7.0	290.9	7.4	306.8	7.6	315.7
	Yield		Net profit			
	SEM ±	CD (0.05)	SEM ±	CD (0.05)		
Irrigation (I) at same level of cropping sequence (C)	0.1	0.3	6.8	18.9		
C at same level of I	0.1	0.4	8.7	24.3		

^aAv of 6 yr.

irrigation water was kept at 7 cm 3 d after disappearance of ponded water.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with a combination of winter

and summer irrigation in the main plots and cropping sequence in the subplots, replicated three times. Irrigation schedules and amounts for each crop were

Table 1. Irrigation schedules and amounts for each crop of different sequences. Bihar, India. 1986-91.

Irrigation level	Wheat		Maize		Potato		Indian mustard		Gram		Green gram and black gram	
	Schedule (IW:CPE) ^a	Amount (cm)	Schedule (IW:CPE)	Amount (cm)	Schedule (IW:CPE)	Amount (cm)	Schedule (DAS) ^b	Amount (cm)	Schedule (DAS)	Amount (cm)	Schedule (DAS)	Amount (cm)
Suboptimal	0.5	12	0.5	18	0.6	12	Rainfed	0	Rainfed	0	Rainfed	0
Optimal	0.7	18	0.7	24	0.9	12	60	6	45	6	30	6
Supraoptimal	0.9	24	0.9	30	1.2	18	30, 60	12	45, 75	12	20, 40	12

^aIW:CPE = irrigation water depth - cumulative pan evaporation ratio. ^bDAS = days after sowing.